

DELIVERABLE 7.1

RELISH Platform Prototype

First Iteration

Prepared by Augusto Esteves, IST

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D7.1 Overview

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AUTHOR(S)	Augusto Esteves
CONTRIBUTOR(S)	Gianni Tumedei, Andrea Cristiano, Luiz Sachser, João Bravo
APPROVER	H. Rosi Song

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1.0	30/06/2026	H. Rosi Song	Coordinator Approval and Final Submission

Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	PC	Project Coordinator
clCH	culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage	SoS	System of Systems
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	T[No.]	Task [No.]
EC	European Commission	UC[No.]	Use-Case [No.]
GA	Grant Agreement	WP[No.]	Work Package [No.]

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy
Partner	University of Toronto	UoT	Canada

Legal disclaimer

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 7.1 (D7.1) of the Horizon Europe-funded RELISH project provides an overview of the first iteration of the RELISH web platform, which aims to preserve and reframe European culinary heritage through digital and AI-powered technologies. The platform leverages a System of Systems (SoS) architecture.

The report provides early access and design details for four core **Use-Cases (UCs)** currently comprising the platform. Moving forward, the platform is slated to expand with additional UCs, including an interactive food-sustainability map and a spatial-computing AI cooking companion.

The first iteration platform prototype architecture and UCs were completed within WP7, led by IST.

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU’s common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

Deliverable 7.1 (D7.1) complements **D7.2**¹ – a detailed description of the technical work behind the RELISH web platform – to provide an overview and early access to:

- The RELISH web platform’s architecture, first iteration (see **Table 1**);
- The design and development of four of the seven Use-Cases (UCs) that currently comprise the RELISH platform (see **Tables 2–5**).

The platform’s ongoing design and development is conducted by WP7, led by IST, in consultation with the RELISH consortium.

1.1 Overview of Platform Prototype, First Iteration

This demonstrator outlines the platform’s **System of Systems (SoS)** architecture, deployed on VMCloud, which enables individual UCs to operate autonomously with isolated databases and independent technology stacks, maintaining strict data boundaries.

The report provides early access and design details for four core **UCs** currently comprising the platform:

- UC1 – A browser-based application facilitating “Food Memories” narrative cooking workshops;

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/21044258>

- UC3 – A novel “Recipes’ Digital Twin” that uses AI to monitor real-world, near real-time cooking practices extracted from social media;
- UC4 – A graph-based “Shopping Recommender” encouraging sustainable, seasonal eating through a Telegram bot and web application;
- UC5 – A “Youth Survey on Food Culture” capturing the culinary identities and future expectations of young people (UC5).

Moving forward, the platform is slated to expand with additional UCs, including an interactive food-sustainability map and a spatial-computing AI cooking companion.

2 Platform Architecture

Table 1: Summary of the RELISH platform’s architecture (T7.1), SoS, which comprises various UCs.

Name (Task)	RELISH Platform’s Architecture (T7.1)
Diagram / Figure	<p style="text-align: center;">DECOUPLED RELISH SoS ARCHITECTURE</p> <p>Legend</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> System Block (VM & DB) Communication Bus Data Flow
Description	<p>The RELISH platform leverages a System of Systems (SoS) architecture: a federated engineering paradigm in which multiple autonomous, task-oriented constituent systems pool their resources and capabilities to realise a collective, emergent value. This SoS architecture is formally characterised by the operational and managerial independence of its constituent elements, their evolutionary development lifecycles, and their virtual or geographic distribution.</p> <p>Each constituent system (<i>i.e.</i>, UC) functions as an autonomous entity that undergoes its own compilation and deployment pipeline, maintaining a dedicated technology stack, business logic, and isolated database tier tailored to its domain requirements. Interoperability across the platform is strictly decoupled, relying on sparse, well-defined data exchanges to preserve absolute domain boundaries and prevent horizontal privilege escalation across systems.</p>
Lead(s) @ IST	Augusto Esteves, Gianni Tumedei, Luiz Sachser, João Bravo
Access	The RELISH platform is deployed in VMCloud, an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) platform and private cloud service hosted at IST’s data centres. Public access is carried out via individual UCs.
Future Work	The platform will be expanded with at least two novel UCs: UC2 will lead to an interactive map for the web based on the food sustainability impact data (T3.4) and survey data (T3.2, T3.3); while UC6 will lead to a spatial computing, AI cooking companion prototype that detects and responds to everyday cooking actions.

3 Early View Use-Cases

3.1 Use-Case 1

Table 2: Summary of UC1 – Food Memories (T7.2).

Name (Task)	Food Memories (T7.2)
<p>Diagram / Figure</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>This system is a browser-based facilitator companion application that supports the two-day Food Memories workshop methodology developed by the RELISH consortium (D3.1). The Food Memories workshop brings together participants to explore culinary memory, Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), and speculative recipe-making through a structured sequence of activities combining narrative writing, memory mapping, collaborative cooking, and reflective tasting.</p> <p>Our system operationalises this methodology by providing facilitators with a real-time digital console that mirrors the workshop's phased structure, whilst also collecting, managing, and preserving the documentary outputs of each session. Our system follows a classic three-tier web application architecture, separated into a React-based single-page application frontend, a Node.js/Express REST API backend, and a MongoDB document database. The three tiers run as independent processes that communicate over HTTP.</p>
<p>Lead(s) @ IST</p>	<p>Augusto Esteves, Luiz Sachser</p>

Access	The system is currently being deployed in IST's data centres. Early development and user testing was carried out on Google's Cloud Platform (see Figure above). Open-source access is being considered pending further IP discussions with UA and RUC.
Future Work	Complete the migration of our companion application to IST's data centres; carry out further user tests in September 2026 (M20); refactor our frontend component into feature-specific sub-components and a shared context or state manager; enable concurrent facilitator access ; implement photo compression; <i>etc.</i>

3.2 Use-Case 3

Table 3: Summary of UC3 – Recipes’ Digital Twin (T7.4).

Name (Task)	Recipes’ Digital Twin (T7.4)
Diagram / Figure	
Description	<p>We explored how the Digital Twin (DT) paradigm can be adapted to better account for the distinctive characteristics of Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH). Building on this perspective, we introduce the first digital twin of a culinary recipe that leverages AI-based analysis of social media content to monitor real-world cooking practices in near real time.</p> <p>We adopted a layered approach. The reality layer, often referred to as the physical layer in traditional DTs, provides sources of culinary data, including social media platforms, cooking datasets, and other recipe repositories. The ingestion layer interfaces with these sources, extracting non-structured and semi-structured information such as videos, text, images, and metadata. The layer then converts data into a format compatible with the storage layer. This process involves parsing recipe content, identifying entities such as ingredients or tools, and reusing previously known entities where applicable. A separate modelling and prediction layer interacts with the storage and service layers to perform analyses, trend detection, simulations, and forecasting. The service layer exposes the means to interact with the twin, such as APIs and command-line interfaces. Finally, the app layer includes all front-facing applications based on the DT that query, visualise, and manipulate recipe data.</p>
Lead(s) @ IST	Augusto Esteves, Gianni Tumedei
Access	The system is currently being deployed in IST’s data centres as an online service (<i>software as service, SaaS</i>). The latest version of the prototype’s

	source code is publicly available on GitHub: https://github.com/gtumedei/relish-recipe-dt/releases/tag/v0.1.0
Future Work	Complete the deployment of our system to IST's data centres; design and develop two example applications that leverage our service; <i>etc.</i>

3.3 Use-Case 4

Table 4: Summary of UC4 – Shopping Recommender (T7.5).

Name (Task)	Shopping Recommender: Seasonality & Preferred Cuisines (T7.5)
Diagram / Figure	
Description	<p>Seasonal eating encourages consuming ingredients at their natural peak of availability and can offer benefits in nutrition, sustainability, and affordability. In parallel, computational gastronomy is a data-driven approach to studying recipes, ingredients, and cuisines, drawing on methods from network science, statistics, and machine learning. In particular, graph-based approaches have been used to model ingredient co-occurrence, ingredient types, and recipe similarity, offering a solid foundation for recommendation systems and culinary analysis.</p> <p>As such, we developed a seasonal ingredient recommendation system designed to raise awareness of seasonal produce available in Europe year-round and simplify grocery shopping for users. The aim is for our system to propose ingredient sets that pair well with both the anchor ingredient and one another, encouraging users to experiment more confidently with seasonal cooking and, over time, to make seasonal ingredients part of everyday or spontaneous purchasing habits.</p>
Lead(s) @ IST	Augusto Esteves, Andrea Cristiano
Access	Our system is accessible through two interfaces: a Telegram bot (@ingredient_recommendation_bot) that supports direct, lightweight

	interaction and allows users to obtain the necessary information quickly while shopping; and a web application that, by contrast, is intended to display the underlying architecture more explicitly, showing how ingredients interact within each cuisine through the graphs (currently being deployed in IST's data centres).
Future Work	Complete the deployment of our web application to IST's data centres; design and develop a mobile application that expands our bot; etc.

3.4 Use-Case 5

Table 5: Summary of UC5 – Youth Survey on Food Culture (T7.6).

Name (Task)	Youth Survey on Food Culture (T7.6)	
Diagram / Figure		
Description	<p>We designed and deployed a family of online surveys that capture how primarily young people describe their food practices, culinary identity, and expectations for the future. The <i>Food & Culture Questionnaire</i> covers demographics, cooking habits and confidence, household arrangements, iconic and everyday dishes, key ingredients, food-related social-media use, dietary preferences, and the role of food in personal, regional, and national identity. The <i>Futures Survey</i> captures ordinal judgements about the respondent’s outlook for themselves, their country, Europe, and the world. Lastly, the <i>Food Visions/Images About the Future</i> exercise invites participants to write a short narrative, “A Day in the Life in 2050,” eliciting rich qualitative visions of everyday food futures.</p> <p>To date, we have collected 877 responses across the three instruments. Our implementation follows a typical MERN stack with Claude being used normalises noisy free-text food data.</p>	
Lead(s) @ IST	Augusto Esteves, João Bravo	
Access	<i>Food & Culture Questionnaire</i>	Survey: https://relish-platform.eu/youth_survey Dashboard: https://relish-platform.eu/youth_dashboard

Name (Task)	Youth Survey on Food Culture (T7.6)	
	<i>Futures Survey</i>	Survey: https://relish-platform.eu/futures_survey Dashboard: https://relish-platform.eu/futures_dashboard
	<i>Food Visions Images About the Future</i>	Survey: https://relish-platform.eu/futures_narratives Dashboard: https://relish-platform.eu/futures_narratives_dashboard
Future Work	Complete deployment of our web application to IST's data centres; design and develop a mobile application that expands our bot; etc.	